

Title: Surface chemistry for NEET and JEE students in One Page

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Abstract

Surface chemistry is the study of what happens at the edges of different phases, like solid–liquid, solid–gas, and liquid–gas. This review talks about the basic ideas behind adsorption, catalysis, and colloidal systems. It covers their types, how they work, and how they are used in biological and industrial systems. The study focuses on Freundlich's adsorption isotherm, heterogeneous and homogeneous catalysis, and the creation, purification, and categorization of colloids. A mind mapping framework is used to assist learners grasp how surface interactions affect processes including drug action, catalysis, and corrosion control by showing how these ideas are connected.

Key Words

Surface chemistry, Adsorption, Catalysis, Colloids, Enzyme catalysis, Freundlich isotherm, Mind mapping

SURFACE CHEMISTRY

Types

- Oil dispersed in water (O/w type) Milk
- Water dispersed in oil (W/O type) Butter

Dispersion of one liquid into another liquid which is immiscible

FREUNDLICH ADSORPTION THEOREM

$$\frac{x}{m} = K \cdot p^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (n > 1)$$

$$\log \frac{x}{m} = \log K + \frac{1}{n} \log p$$

Adsorption isotherm means to express variation in the amount adsorption with pressure at constant temperature

- APPLICATION**
- Purification of drinking water.
 - Medicines
 - Rubber Industry
 - Industrial Production

Enzyme that catalyse many life processes in living organisms are termed as Biochemical catalysts known as Biochemical catalysis.

Mechanism

Step 1: Binding of enzyme to substrate to form an activated complex

$$E + S \rightarrow ES^*$$

- Lock and key theory
- Induced fit theory

Mechanism

Step 2: Decomposition of activated complex to form product

$$ES^* \rightarrow E + p$$

Substance which alter the rate of reaction and remain chemically and quantitatively unchanged after the reaction are known as catalyst and phenomenon is known as catalysis.

Shape selective

Catalytic reaction that depends upon pore structure of catalyst and size of reactant and product molecule (Zeolites)

PHYSISSORPTION

- It is reversible.
- Simply on surface of adsorbent by weak van der Waals forces.
- Low temperature and high pressure are favourable

CHEMISORPTION

- Irreversible process
- Simply on surface of adsorbent via chemical bonds.
- High temperature and high pressure is favourable.

Accumulation of molecular particles of at the surface rather than in the bulk of a solid or liquid is known as Adsorption. It is a surface phenomenon.

Types of catalysis

- Multimolecular colloids: large no. of atoms/molecules aggregate (size < 1 nm)
- Macromolecular colloids: large molecules (Polymers)
- Associated: Low concentration colloids like normal electrolytes

- Lyophilic Colloids: Solvent loving
- Lyophobic colloids: Solvent hating

Classification Based on Physical State

Dispersed Phase	Dispersion Medium	Type of Colloid	Example
Gas	Liquid	Foam	Shaving Cream
Gas	Solid	Solid Sol	Pumice Stone
Liquid	Gas	Liquid aerosol	Fog
Liquid	Liquid	Emulsion	Milk
Liquid	Solid	Gel	Butter
Solid	Gas	Solid aerosol	Dust
Solid	Liquid	Sol	Ink
Solid	Solid	Solid Sol	Alloys

- PURIFICATION**
- Dialysis
 - Electrodialysis
 - Ultra filtration

- COLLIGATIVE PROPERTIES**
- Tyndall effect
 - Brownian Motion

METHODS OF PREPARATION

- DISPERSION METHOD**
- Mechanical
 - Bredig's arc

- CONDENSATION METHOD**
- Peptization
 - Exchange of solvent

- CHEMICAL METHOD**
- Oxidation
 - Reduction
 - Hydrolysis
 - Double decomposition method

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